

The Mediating Role Of Green Organizational Identity And Corporate Social Responsibility On The Impact Of Sustainable Leadership On Green Creativity In The Aviation Industry

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Abstract

Increasing environmental problems and sustainability pressure increase the importance of environmentally focused leadership approaches in organizations. In this context, it is important to understand how sustainable leadership affects employees' innovative behaviors towards the environment. The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of sustainable leadership on green creativity and to reveal the mediating role of green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility in this relationship. The research data were collected from 411 participants working in the aviation industry through a survey method, and the data were analyzed using structural equation modeling. The results of the analysis show that sustainable leadership has positive and significant effects on green organizational identity ($\beta=0.706$), corporate social responsibility ($\beta=0.655$), and green creativity ($\beta=0.314$). In addition, green organizational identity ($\beta=0.357$) and corporate social responsibility ($\beta=0.149$) have significant effects on green creativity. Mediation analyses reveal that green organizational identity ($\beta=0.252$) and corporate social responsibility ($\beta=0.098$) play a partial mediating role in the relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity. When the explanatory level of the model is analyzed, it is seen that 53% of the variance in green creativity ($R^2=0.530$) is explained. Research findings show that sustainable leadership practices play an important role in developing employees' environmentally oriented creative behaviors.

Key words: Sustainable Leadership, Green Creativity, Green Organizational Identity, Corporate Social Responsibility, Structural Equation Modeling, Aviation Industry.

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1. Introduction

The aviation industry is one of the most pressurized sectors in terms of reducing global carbon emissions, increasing environmental efficiency, and implementing sustainability policies at the corporate level (Sgouridis et al., 2011; Sher et al., 2021). In line with increasing environmental sensitivity, international regulations, and public expectations, the strategic importance of environmental practices in airline companies is increasing. In this context, sustainable leadership, which refers to the ability of managers to transform organizational culture on the basis of environmental sensitivity, is considered a critical factor in increasing both the competitiveness and environmental performance of organizations (Avery & Bergsteiner, 2012). Considering the long-term life cycle, safety standards, and environmental obligations of aviation industry businesses, a sustainable leadership approach has become a strategic imperative in the sector (Thepchalerm & Pinsuwan, 2025).

Sustainable leadership is not limited to reducing carbon footprint or promoting environmentally friendly practices, but also refers to a cultural transformation that involves employees' environmental awareness, environmental values, and organizational commitment (McCann & Holt, 2009). One of the important outcomes of this transformation is green creativity, which shows the capacity of organizational employees to develop environmentally friendly products, processes, and services, and as green innovation becomes a determinant of competition, employees' ability to generate and implement green ideas is considered an important indicator of success in the aviation industry (Chen & Chang, 2013). At this point, green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility emerge as two important concepts in explaining the impact of sustainable leadership on employee behaviors. Green organizational identity is formed when organizational members perceive that they are part of an environmentally sensitive organization, and it creates a strong psychological commitment to environmentalist behaviors in employees (Chen, 2011). According to the social identity theory, individuals see the identity of the organization they belong to as a part of their own identity and exhibit behaviors compatible with the organization (Khan et al., 2025).

Corporate social responsibility refers to the level of fulfillment of environmental, social, and ethical responsibilities of organizations and significantly shapes employees' perceptions of the organization (Glavas & Kelley, 2014). In the aviation industry, corporate social responsibility practices such as carbon offset projects, sustainable fuel use, waste management, social projects, and environmental awareness training strengthen the environmental awareness of the organization among employees and encourage their innovative environmental behaviors (Lee & Mo, 2011; Wong et al., 2020).

This study aims to examine the impact of sustainable leadership on green creativity in the context of the aviation industry and to address the mediating roles

of green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility in this relationship. In the literature, studies focusing on the aviation sector are quite limited, and it is seen that a holistic model in which variables are examined together is missing. For this reason, it is hoped that the study will both contribute to the theoretical literature and provide important findings that can guide strategic management for aviation sector enterprises.

2. Conceptual Framework

Studies conducted in the field of organizational sustainability show that variables such as leadership, organizational identity, creativity, and social responsibility are closely interrelated. Therefore, the conceptual framework of the study aims to systematically address the theoretical foundations of the basic concepts in the research model. In this context, the concepts of sustainable leadership, green creativity, green organizational identity, and corporate social responsibility are examined in detail based on the literature, and the theoretical integrity of the model is revealed.

2.1. Sustainable Leadership

Sustainable leadership refers to a management approach that addresses economic, social, and environmental dimensions in a holistic manner, which has gained increasing importance in the leadership literature in recent years (Avery & Bergsteiner, 2012). Unlike traditional leadership approaches, sustainable leadership is a comprehensive leadership model that aims to secure the long-term existence of the organization, the ecological balance, and the well-being of stakeholders, rather than focusing only on short-term performance and profitability goals (Nie et al., 2025). Today, this approach has become an important element that reshapes the strategic orientations of organizations as the concept of sustainability has become central to corporate governance practices (Rehman et al., 2019).

Sustainable leadership is often explained in the literature through three main dimensions: economic sustainability, social sustainability, and environmental sustainability (Tideman et al., 2013). The economic dimension encompasses the effective use of resources to ensure that the organization maintains its competitive power in the long term; social sustainability includes employee welfare, ethical values, and stakeholder relations; and environmental sustainability includes the adoption of environmentally friendly practices. Managing this triad holistically increases the importance of sustainable leadership in organizational change and strategic governance (Šimanskienė & Župerkienė, 2014; Tideman et al., 2013).

Environmental sensitivity is one of the key components of sustainable leadership. Hallinger and Suriyankietkaew (2018) state that sustainable leaders are sensitive to environmental issues, make ethical decisions, build strong relationships with stakeholders, and are effective in conveying the environmental vision of the organization to employees. Leaders' environmental behaviors significantly shape

employees' attitudes towards the environment and organizational climate. Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1986) argues that individuals learn from their leaders through observation and tend to exhibit similar behaviors; therefore, sustainable leadership plays a critical role in the formation of an environmental culture in the organization.

The environmental awareness created by sustainable leaders within the organization supports employees to address business processes from an environmentally friendly perspective and to produce innovative solutions. In this context, it can be said that sustainable leadership is effective in contributing to the formation of a climate where green creativity is supported at the organizational level (Tian & Wang, 2023). Sustainable leadership is critical in industries with intense environmental pressures, such as the aviation sector, where airline companies have to comply with international environmental standards, reduce carbon emissions, adopt sustainable fuel policies, and develop social responsibility projects (Lee & Mo, 2011).

Therefore, sustainable leadership emerges as a key element that strengthens the environmental performance of organizations both operationally and strategically (Khan et al., 2023). In summary, sustainable leadership is a determinant mechanism in organizational environmentalism and innovation processes and represents a strategic leadership approach that directs employee behaviors. Due to these characteristics, it is possible to say that sustainable leadership has strong theoretical links with concepts such as green creativity, green organizational identity, and corporate social responsibility.

2.2. Green Creativity

Green creativity is a concept that refers to the capacity of employees to generate and implement innovative ideas to improve environmental sustainability (Arici & Uysal, 2022; Song & Yu, 2018). Green creativity, introduced to the literature by Chen and Chang (2013), focuses not only on general business creativity, but also on the capacity to produce innovative solutions that are environmentally sensitive, low resource-consuming, reduce carbon footprint, or do not harm nature. In this respect, green creativity is considered a critical organizational output that is at the heart of sustainable business models.

Today, businesses are paying more attention to environmentally friendly innovation processes in the face of increasing environmental pressures and sustainability expectations (Majid et al., 2020). Green creativity is a micro-level mechanism that supports this environmental innovation process. Green creativity is decisive in areas such as green product design, energy saving, reuse processes, and waste reduction, and is actively involved in improving corporate sustainability performance (Al-Ghazali et al., 2022).

One of the most important factors affecting the emergence of green creativity is organizational leadership (Arici & Uysal, 2022). Social Learning

Theory argues that employees adopt the environmental decisions and behaviors of their leaders by observing them, and in this context, environmentally sensitive leadership behaviors increase employees' willingness to generate creative ideas for environmental problems (Bandura, 1986). In studies supporting this relationship, it has been found that environmental leadership behaviors directly contribute to employees' green innovation performance, and it is stated that an organizational climate focused on environmental sustainability causes employees to develop positive attitudes towards the environment, which in turn increases green creativity (Mittal & Dhar, 2016).

Green creativity is also closely related to employees' psychological sense of ownership and organizational belonging (Fang et al., 2021). Employees who embrace the green identity of the organization and see it as their responsibility to contribute to environmental goals tend to generate more green ideas to achieve sustainability goals. Therefore, it is widely supported in the literature that green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility practices improve green creativity (Chen, 2011; Du et al., 2011).

In the aviation industry, green creativity is critical in areas such as sustainable maintenance and repair processes, energy-efficient flight operations, environmentally friendly cabin services, and process improvements based on fuel efficiency. In this context, the generation of environmentally friendly ideas by employees in the aviation sector is a key determinant in achieving the sustainability goals of businesses (Wong et al., 2020). As a result, green creativity is an indispensable organizational factor for sustainable organizations, representing the active role of employees in the green innovation process, and green creativity is influenced by both leadership, organizational identity, and corporate social responsibility practices, and it is consistent with its inclusion as a dependent variable in the model of the study.

2.3. Green Organizational Identity

Green organizational identity is a type of collective organizational identity that emerges when organizational members perceive their organization as an environmentally conscious, environmentally protective, and environmentally responsible structure and internalize this identity (Chang & Chen, 2013; Chen, 2011). This concept is shaped within the framework of social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1986) and argues that individuals make the identity of the organization they belong to a part of their own identity and tend to exhibit behaviors that are compatible with the values of the organization (Tajfel & Turner, 2004).

Green organizational identity is strengthened when an organization adopts environmentally friendly strategies, supports green practices, shares its sustainability vision with employees, and actively improves its environmental performance (Ma et al., 2023). Green organizational identity facilitates employees who want to contribute to the sustainability goals of the organization to exhibit environmentally friendly behaviors, generate innovative ideas, and adhere to the

sustainability vision, and is included in the literature as a critical mediating mechanism in the emergence of green behaviors and green creativity (Ciocirlan, 2017).

Sustainable leadership behaviors are an important determinant for the formation of an organization's green identity. Sustainable leaders place environmental responsibility at the center of organizational culture and thus help employees develop a strong sense of green identity in the organization (Avery & Bergsteiner, 2012). Environmentally sensitive leadership behaviors enable employees to adopt the values of the organization and direct them to environmentally friendly behaviors. In addition, corporate social responsibility activities of organizations directly contribute to the strengthening of green organizational identity and cause employees to perceive their organizations as a socially and environmentally sensitive actor (Turker, 2009). Green organizational identity is also a source of intrinsic motivation that increases green creativity, and it is seen that employees who perceive their organizational identity as environmentally sensitive increase their level of identification with the organization and are more willing to develop environmentally friendly innovative ideas (Chen, 2011; Ciocirlan, 2017). Therefore, positioning green organizational identity as a mediating variable is consistent with the purpose of the study.

2.4. Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate social responsibility is a multidimensional concept that refers to businesses acting responsibly towards society, the environment, and stakeholders while continuing their economic activities (Du et al., 2011; Glavas & Kelley, 2014). Corporate social responsibility is a comprehensive corporate governance approach that is not limited to economic performance but also includes ethical, environmental, and social values (Turker, 2009). With the strengthening of sustainability movements in the world, corporate social responsibility has become a strategic imperative rather than a preference for businesses (Piercy & Lane, 2011).

Corporate social responsibility practices have a positive impact on both internal and external stakeholders by increasing the environmental management level of organizations. Corporate social responsibility activities have strong effects on employee engagement, organizational citizenship behavior, strengthening firm reputation and innovative performance, and create a sense of pride in the organization (Du et al., 2011). This increases employees' willingness to contribute to organizational goals.

The aviation sector is also considered a critical sector in terms of corporate social responsibility. In this sector with high carbon emissions, businesses are expected to develop environmental responsibility projects, use sustainable aviation fuel, manage waste, and develop environmentally friendly flight operations (Wong et al., 2020). For this reason, the perception of corporate social responsibility in aviation businesses plays a decisive role in employee behaviors, and corporate social responsibility practices constitute an important intrinsic motivation source

that triggers environmentalist behaviors in employees (Kuo et al., 2016). When employees see that their organizations carry out environmentally and socially sensitive projects, they feel part of a more meaningful job, and their tendency to engage in environmentally friendly behaviors increases (Lynes & Andrachuk, 2008).

It is seen that corporate social responsibility practices have a strong relationship with organizational identity and create a strong identity commitment to the organization in employees (Turker, 2009). This commitment helps employees to exhibit behaviors compatible with organizational values and is an institutional mechanism that strengthens both green organizational identity and green creativity. In this context, corporate social responsibility is a powerful corporate governance approach that increases the capacity of organizations to protect the environment, ethical responsibility, and sensitivity to stakeholder expectations. Due to its effects on employee behaviors, its positioning as a mediating variable in your model is also consistent with the literature.

3. Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis Development

In this section, the relationships between the variables in the research model are discussed in line with the relevant literature, and research hypotheses are developed. In this context, the relationships between sustainable leadership, green organizational identity, corporate social responsibility, and green creativity variables are examined within the framework of theoretical foundations.

3.1. The Impact of Sustainable Leadership on Green Organizational Identity

Environmentally sensitive leadership styles deeply affect employees' perceptions of the organization and determine how they define organizational identity. Therefore, sustainable leadership is expected to increase green organizational identity. Green organizational identity refers to organizational members' perception of their organization as a structure that is sensitive to the environment and adopts environmental values (Chen, 2011). According to Social Identity Theory (Tajfel & Turner, 2004), individuals make the organization they belong to a part of their identity, and the characteristics of the organization affect their self-identity. Therefore, the environmental vision of organizational leaders directly affects the way employees identify with the organization and strengthens the formation of green organizational identity.

Sustainable leaders' behaviors represent the organization's environmental sensitivity at both symbolic and behavioral levels, with leaders supporting the organization's adoption of environmentally friendly policies, setting long-term sustainability goals, and providing strategic guidance that instills environmental values in employees (Hallinger & Suriyankietkaew, 2018). These attitudes of leaders increase the likelihood that employees perceive the organization as an environmentally sensitive actor, and in organizations where leaders support

environmentally oriented practices, employees identify the organization with a greener identity (Ciocirlan, 2017).

In addition, sustainable leadership enables the establishment of environmental norms, ethical values, and environmentally sensitive communication within the organization, and the transmission of values through leadership increases the tendency of employees to make the environmental identity of the organization a part of their own identity (Fang et al., 2021). According to the Value Match Model, employees tend to act in accordance with the values adopted by leaders, and their perceptions of the organization's identity are shaped by these values. Therefore, sustainable leadership's strong embedding of environmental values in organizational culture is a critical factor in the process of creating a green organizational identity (Amos & Weathington, 2008).

In the context of the aviation industry, the impact of sustainable leadership on green organizational identity becomes even more important. Airline companies have critical responsibilities such as complying with environmental regulations and reducing carbon emissions. Therefore, leaders' environmental vision facilitates employees' perception of their organization as an environmentally responsible structure and strengthens green organizational identity. In this direction, sustainable leadership is considered a mechanism that conveys the environmental values of the organization to employees in a strong and reliable way and shapes the perception of organizational identity, and within the scope of the study, hypothesis H1 is formed as follows.

H1: Sustainable leadership positively affects green organizational identity.

3.2. The Impact of Sustainable Leadership on Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate social responsibility is a comprehensive corporate governance approach that refers to the ethical, social, and environmental responsibility of businesses towards society, the environment, employees, and all stakeholders while conducting their economic activities (Turker, 2009). In modern organizations, corporate social responsibility has become an integral part of strategic management and sustainability policies, rather than just an activity that responds to social pressures. In this context, leadership plays a decisive role in the realization of corporate social responsibility practices and their adoption by employees (Piercy & Lane, 2011). In particular, sustainable leadership is critical for the institutionalization of social responsibility culture in organizations and its internalization by employees (Pureza & Lee, 2020).

Sustainable leadership offers a leadership approach that considers the environmental and social impacts of organizations, long-term stakeholder interests, and ethical responsibilities (Avery & Bergsteiner, 2012). Leaders' commitment to social responsibility ensures that organizational strategies are created in line with corporate social responsibility, and corporate social responsibility practices can be carried out more systematically and effectively thanks to the ethical behaviors of

sustainable leaders and decision-making mechanisms that take stakeholders into account.

Upper Echelons Theory is an important theory for this relationship. The theory argues that the strategic orientations of organizations are shaped by the values, beliefs, and worldviews of senior managers, and that the environmental and socially responsible values of sustainable leaders are one of the key factors that determine the scope and nature of an organization's corporate social responsibility practices (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). Leaders' sustainability vision has a direct impact on the organization's social responsibility strategies (Galpin & Lee Whittington, 2012).

Social Learning Theory also makes an important contribution to the relationship between sustainable leadership and corporate social responsibility (Bandura, 1986). Employees make inferences about organizational norms by observing the behaviors of leaders and tend to exhibit behaviors in accordance with these norms. Therefore, ethical, environmentalist, and responsible behaviors of sustainable leaders create a strong perception among employees about the value that the organization places on social responsibility (Boeske, 2023). This perception facilitates the adoption and diffusion of a corporate social responsibility culture in the organization.

One of the reasons why sustainable leaders increase CSR practices in organizations is the stakeholder management approach. Sustainable leadership takes into account the expectations of stakeholders, makes decisions to minimize environmental and social impacts, and ensures that CSR projects are integrated into strategic plans (Hallinger & Suriyankietkaew, 2018). This approach allows employees to perceive the organization's social responsibility culture in a more visible and meaningful way. In this context, it is understood that sustainable leadership is a fundamental mechanism that both structures the corporate social responsibility activities of organizations and shapes the way they are perceived by employees. In this context, it can be strongly observed that sustainable leadership has a significant and positive effect on corporate social responsibility practices and employees' perceptions of corporate social responsibility. The H2 hypothesis developed within the scope of the study was formed in this direction as follows.

H2: Sustainable leadership positively affects the perception of corporate social responsibility.

3.3. The Impact of Sustainable Leadership on Green Creativity

Sustainable leadership is a multifaceted leadership model that aims to create long-term value for the organization by considering economic, social, and environmental dimensions in a holistic manner (Avery & Bergsteiner, 2012). This leadership approach significantly shapes employees' environmental behaviors, organizational values, and sustainability-oriented ways of doing their jobs (Tian & Wang, 2023). Therefore, sustainable leadership is expected to support green creativity, which is one of the key components of green innovation and sustainable business models.

Green creativity is the capacity of employees to develop new environmentally sensitive ideas, propose environmentally friendly processes and products, and make innovative contributions to improve sustainability performance (Chen & Chang, 2013). Accordingly, it is increasingly recognized in the literature that sustainable leaders are effective in strengthening employees' level of green creativity.

Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1986) provides an important theoretical basis for explaining this relationship. According to the theory, employees observe leaders' behaviors and reflect them on their own behaviors. When sustainable leaders support environmentally friendly practices, are careful in resource use, give importance to ethical decision-making processes, and communicate long-term environmental goals to employees, employees model these behaviors.

Another important theoretical framework is the Value Match Model. According to this model, the likelihood of employees behaving in line with organizational values depends on the extent to which they identify with the values espoused by the organization and its leaders, and when sustainable leaders place environmental values and ethical principles at the center of the organization, employees tend to act in line with these values. This alignment strengthens the search for creative solutions to environmental problems (Amos & Weathington, 2008). Chen and Chang (2013) also state that leaders' environmental values directly contribute to employees' green innovation process.

In addition, sustainable leadership provides psychological security to employees, and according to the Psychological Security Theory, employees behave more creatively in an environment where making mistakes is not punished, and innovative suggestions are supported (Edmondson, 1999). Sustainable leadership creates a business environment that supports risk-taking for environmental innovations, and in this environment, employees are willing to contribute to sustainable business processes by expressing their environmental ideas (Boeske, 2023).

Accordingly, the theoretical and empirical evidence strongly support that sustainable leadership increases employees' level of green creativity. Based on the relevant research findings and literature, hypothesis H3 is formulated as follows.

H3: Sustainable leadership positively affects green creativity.

3.4. The Impact of Green Organizational Identity on Green Creativity

Green organizational identity is a type of collective identity that emerges as a result of employees' perception of their organizations as a structure that is sensitive to the environment, adopts sustainability principles, and makes environmental protection a part of the organizational mission (Chen, 2011). This identity perception is shaped depending on the level of environmental responsibility of the organization, the environment-oriented vision of the leaders, the sustainability strategies implemented within the organization, and the environmentalist nature of corporate

policies (Ma et al., 2023). In enterprises with a strong green organizational identity, employees see themselves as part of an organization that contributes to the environment and tend to engage in more environmentally friendly behaviors as a requirement of this identity (Elshaer et al., 2024). In this framework, green organizational identity is expected to increase the level of green creativity of employees. Green creativity refers to the ability of employees to develop innovative ideas for environmental problems, provide resource efficiency in processes, make creative contributions that reduce carbon footprint, or produce environmentally friendly solutions (Chen & Chang, 2013).

The main theoretical framework explaining this relationship is the Social Identity Theory, and according to the theory, individuals tend to behave in accordance with organizational values by making the identity of the organization they belong to a part of their personal identity (Tajfel & Turner, 2004). When there is a strong perception that the organization has an environmentalist identity, employees become more open to generating new environment-oriented ideas by behaving as required by this identity, adopt the “green” identity of the organization, and voluntarily exhibit creative behaviors in accordance with this identity (Al-Ghazali et al., 2022).

Green organizational identity also increases employees' intrinsic motivation. Ciocirlan (2017) states that employees who have a strong identity bond with the organization perform environmentally friendly behaviors more voluntarily, develop innovative ideas in line with organizational values, and perform higher in green tasks, and this psychological commitment creates an emotional power source that triggers green creativity.

In addition, Psychological Ownership Theory explains the effect of employees' identification processes with the organization on creative behaviors, and states that when employees identify with the organization, they see the organization's environmental mission as their responsibility and voluntarily make efforts to make environmentally friendly improvements (Pierce et al., 2001). In this context, green organizational identity emerges as an important tool that supports employees to exhibit creative behaviors that are compatible with organizational goals.

Considering the critical importance of environmental performance and sustainability practices in the context of the aviation industry, the impact of green organizational identity on green creativity becomes even more evident. Employees' perception of their organization as an environmentally friendly, responsible, and sustainable structure also encourages them to make creative contributions such as energy saving, waste reduction, and developing environmentally friendly solutions in operational processes (Bahzar, 2019). In this context, the existing theoretical framework and empirical findings strongly support that green organizational identity increases employees' level of green creativity. Accordingly, the H4 hypothesis, which is theoretically consistent and supported by the literature, is formed as follows.

H4: Green organizational identity positively affects green creativity.

3.5. The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Green Creativity

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) refers to the adoption of a management approach that is sensitive to stakeholders by taking into account environmental, ethical, and social responsibilities while maintaining the economic objectives of businesses (Piercy & Lane, 2011; Pureza & Lee, 2020). In recent years, CSR has become central to sustainability-oriented corporate strategies and has become one of the main determinants of the environmental performance of organizations (Garcia et al., 2021). Research on the impact of CSR practices on employee behaviors shows that these practices affect not only external stakeholder perceptions but also employee attitudes, motivation, and innovative behaviors (Du et al., 2011).

Green creativity includes behaviors such as employees developing environmentally friendly processes, generating green product and service ideas, and offering creative solutions to increase resource efficiency (Chang & Chen, 2013). In order for this creativity to emerge, employees need both environmental sensitivity and a strong psychological commitment to the organization, and CSR practices increase the motivation of employees to engage in green creative behaviors by activating this psychological connection (Mozes et al., 2011).

Social Identity Theory provides an important basis for explaining this relationship. According to Tajfel and Turner (1986), individuals make the identity of the organization they belong to a part of their own identity. When organizations adopt a strong CSR vision, employees perceive their organizations as an ethical, environmentally responsible, and value-adding actor; this identity perception increases employees' willingness to engage in behaviors that contribute to the environment, thus green creativity becomes a form of behavior that is compatible with the social responsibility values of the organization (Song et al., 2023).

Another theoretical approach that explains the impact of CSR on green creativity is the Organizational Support Theory. According to this theory, employees tend to contribute more to organizational goals when they believe that the organization values them and society (Paillé & Meija-Morelos, 2019; Ramus, 2001). CSR shows that the organization is not only focused on economic interests, but also cares about the well-being of society and the environment, and this creates a strong “perception of organizational support” in employees. Employees with a high perception of support show more creative efforts to contribute to the environmental goals of the organization (Brammer et al., 2015; Hameed et al., 2019).

In the aviation sector, CSR is of particular importance; in this sector, which is associated with high carbon emissions and environmental risks, CSR practices give employees a strong corporate message about sustainability. This, in turn,

provides a strong source of intrinsic motivation for employees to develop creative ideas in this direction (Lynes & Andrachuk, 2008). In this direction, the existing literature and theoretical approaches clearly show that CSR significantly affects employees' environmentally friendly creative behaviors, and the hypothesis H5 is formed as follows.

H5: Corporate social responsibility positively affects green creativity.

3.6. The Mediating Role of Green Organizational Identity in the Relationship between Sustainable Leadership and Green Creativity

Green organizational identity emerges as an important psychological mechanism in explaining the relationship between sustainable leadership and employees' level of green creativity. Green organizational identity is a form of organizational belonging that is formed as a result of employees' perception of their organizations as a structure that is sensitive to the environment, cares about environmentally friendly practices, and makes environmental sustainability a strategic goal (Chang & Chen, 2013; Chen, 2011). This identity perception increases the level of integration of individuals with the organization and encourages them to act in accordance with the environmental goals of the organization, and a significant part of the impact of sustainable leadership on employees' green creativity is a process expected to be realized through green organizational identity (Zhang et al., 2025).

This mediating relationship is based on the Social Identity Theory, which states that individuals tend to make the identity of the organization to which they belong a part of their own self-identity and behave in accordance with the organizational identity (Tajfel & Turner, 1986). When sustainable leaders create an organizational climate that embraces values such as environmental protection, ethical management, and sustainability, employees begin to identify their organizations with a strong "green" identity. Such an identity becomes not only a means of belonging for employees, but also a source of intrinsic motivation for environmentally friendly behaviors (Kulkarni, 2015). Sustainable leadership is the most important factor that enables the institutionalization of environmental values in the organization, and Avery and Bergsteiner (2011) argue that sustainable leaders unite employees around the environmental vision and improve the long-term environmental performance of the organization. This leadership style facilitates the formation of a green organizational identity by strongly communicating the organization's environmental mission to employees. Ciocirlan (2017) also found that environmentally responsible leadership practices support employees' perception of their organization as a green structure.

Green organizational identity is a powerful psychological mechanism that increases employees' level of green creativity. Norton, Zacher, and Ashkanasy (2014) show that employees who perceive the organization with an environmentally sensitive identity are more likely to engage in environmentally friendly innovative behaviors (Norton et al., 2014). In this context, organizational identity emerges as a variable that directly affects employees' tendency to produce creative solutions to

environmental problems. Chen (2011) also states that a strong perception of green identity leads employees to contribute more to green product design, process improvements, and environmental innovation activities.

In this direction, it shows that sustainable leaders affect employees' green creativity levels both directly and indirectly. The indirect effect mechanism is that sustainable leadership strengthens environmental values within the organization. These values enable employees to perceive the organization with a strong green identity, and employees who internalize green organizational identity voluntarily increase environmental creativity. Therefore, there is a significant mediation process from sustainable leadership to green organizational identity and from green organizational identity to green creativity. Both theoretical models and empirical studies show that green organizational identity plays an important mediating role in the relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity, and accordingly, the H6 hypothesis developed within the scope of the study is formed as follows.

H6: Green organizational identity mediates the relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity.

3.7. The Mediating Role of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Relationship between Sustainable Leadership and Green Creativity

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) stands out as an important institutional and psychological mediating mechanism in explaining the relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity. CSR is a multidimensional corporate governance approach that refers to businesses acting responsibly towards society, the environment, and stakeholders (Brammer et al., 2015). CSR practices not only inform employees about the ethical stance of the organization, but also directly affect how employees perceive their organizations and their motivation towards organizational goals (Hameed et al., 2019). Therefore, the mediating role of CSR is critical to understand how sustainable leadership affects employees' green creativity behaviors.

Sustainable leadership is inherently ethical, environmental, and stakeholder-oriented, and Avery and Bergsteiner (2011) state that sustainable leaders develop a long-term vision to improve the social and environmental performance of the organization and share this vision with employees. This leadership approach ensures that CSR activities are implemented more systematically and visibly in the organization. McCann and Holt (2009) state that sustainable leaders are more sensitive about ethical decision-making and integrating social values into the organizational structure, which increases the quality of CSR practices (McCann & Holt, 2009). The main theoretical framework explaining the mediating role of CSR in this relationship is the Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1986). Employees make inferences about the values of the organization by observing the socially responsible behaviors of their leaders and model these behaviors, and the importance given by

leaders to CSR creates a strong perception in employees that the organization is socially and environmentally responsible (Jones Christensen et al., 2014). This psychological perception contributes significantly to employees' environmentally friendly and innovative behaviors.

In this context, the indirect relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity can be explained as follows: Sustainable leadership ensures the institutionalization of CSR in the organization, CSR activities strengthen the perception of employees that the organization is environmentally and socially responsible, and employees exhibit green creativity behaviors by acting in accordance with organizational values in line with this perception.

This mechanism shows the existence of a significant mediation process of sustainable leadership towards CSR and CSR towards green creativity. The findings of Du et al. (2011) also confirm that leadership increases the perception of CSR, and this has a positive effect on employees' innovative behaviors. In this context, both theoretical explanations and empirical findings strongly suggest that CSR plays an important mediating role in the relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity, and hypothesis H7, which is based on theoretical foundations and supported by the literature, is formed as follows.

H7: Corporate social responsibility mediates the relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity.

In accordance with the hypotheses, the research model in Figure 1 was created as follows.

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: Created by authors.

4. Method

The aviation sector is of great importance in the service sector worldwide and in Turkey, and attracts attention especially due to developments in sustainability and mandatory practices. It is thought that the sector will be subject to some restrictions due to high CO₂ and NO₂ emissions. With this study, it is planned to measure whether the sector has taken any action to address the impending threat and its effectiveness. For this purpose, the study aims to evaluate the mediating role of green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility in the effect of sustainable leadership understanding of aviation sector employees on green creativity and to contribute the findings to the literature. The sample of the study consists of 411 participants working in the aviation sector in Giresun, Trabzon, and Istanbul provinces. The research consists of 23 questions filled in face-to-face or digitally on a voluntary basis in Giresun, Trabzon, and Istanbul. 411 people working in the aviation sector between August 01, 2025, and December 31, 2025, participated in the research, which is based on volunteerism, being over the age of 18, and not having mental disabilities, and using a convenience sampling method. Before the research, the ethical permission of Giresun University Social Sciences, Science and Engineering Sciences Research Ethics Committee dated July 02, 2025, and numbered Decision: 07/389-GD dated July 04, 2025. In addition, the participants were informed about the research with a consent form.

In the study, data were obtained by using scales consisting of 23 questions: the Sustainable Leadership Scale, the Corporate Social Responsibility Scale, the Green Organizational Identity Scale, and the Green Creativity Scale. Personal Information Form: The questions prepared by the researcher include 6 items to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants. The Sustainable Leadership Scale developed by Achmad and Wiratmadja (2024) was used to measure sustainable leadership in the study, and the scale consists of 6 questions. In order to measure corporate social responsibility, the Social Responsibility Scale

Lichtenstein et al. (2004), consisting of 5 questions, was used, and the Green Organizational Identity Scale, developed by Chen (2011), consisting of 6 questions, was used to measure green organizational identity. In order to measure green creativity, the Green Creativity Scale developed by Chen and Chang (2013), consisting of 6 questions, was used, and all scales are 5-point Likert-type. The data obtained were analyzed with the Smart-PLS program, and Structural Equation Modeling was conducted with the relevant programs, and the hypotheses prepared in accordance with the literature were discussed within the scope of the model.

5. Findings

In this study, 411 people working in the aviation sector were reached, and detailed socio-demographic information of the individuals participating in the study is presented in Table 1. The variables in the table are analyzed under six main demographic headings: gender, marital status, age, education level, professional experience, and income level. These data are important in terms of revealing the general profile of the sample and showing in which context the research results are obtained. The demographic information of the participants in the study is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Information

Demographic	Variable	n	%
Gender	Female	126	30.66
	Male	285	69.34
Marital Status	Married	249	60.58
	Single	162	39.42
Age	Between 18-30 Years Old	74	18.00
	Between 31-40 Years Old	162	39.42
	Between 41-50 Years Old	115	27.98
	51 Years Old and Above	60	14.60
Educational Status	Associate Degree	51	12.41
	Bachelor's Degree	281	68.37
	Postgraduate Degree	75	18.25
	Doctorate Degree	4	0.97
Experience	5 Years and Below	92	22.38
	Between 6-10 Years	154	37.47
	Between 11-15 Years	94	22.87
	Between 16-20 Years	51	12.41
	21 Years and Above	20	4.87
Income	Between 40.000-60.000 TL	87	21.17
	Between 60.001-80.000 TL	124	30.17
	Between 80.001-100.000 TL	95	23.11
	Between 100.001-120.000 TL	83	20.20
	120.001 TL and Above	22	5.35

Source: Tabulated by the authors

First of all, when the gender distribution of the participants is analyzed, it is seen that 30.66% of the sample is female (n=126) and 69.34% is male (n=285). This distribution shows that male participants have a numerically higher proportion among the individuals participating in the study. When the age distribution of the participants is analyzed, it is seen that there are four different age groups. Accordingly, 18.00% of the participants were between the ages of 18-30, 39.42% were between the ages of 31-40, 27.98% were between the ages of 41-50, and 14.60% were 51 years and older. These findings show that the age group with the highest proportion in the sample is the 31-40 age range. When the educational status of the participants is analyzed, it is seen that a significant portion of the sample has a bachelor's degree. Accordingly, 12.41% of the participants were associate degree graduates, 68.37% were bachelor's degree graduates, 18.25% were postgraduate graduates, and 0.97% were doctoral graduates. According to this distribution, the highest rate belongs to bachelor's graduates, while the lowest rate belongs to the doctoral graduates group.

When the professional experience of the individuals participating in the study is analyzed, it is seen that the participants are distributed in different experience ranges. Accordingly, 22.38% of the participants have 5 years of experience or less, 37.47% have 6-10 years of experience, 22.87% have 11-15 years of experience, 12.41% have 16-20 years of experience, and 4.87% have 21 years of experience or more. These results show that the highest proportion of the sample consists of participants with 6-10 years of experience. It is also seen that most of the participants have 15 years of experience or less.

In general, the demographic characteristics of the individuals participating in the study are distributed across different age, education, experience, and income groups. While the majority of the participants are male, married individuals are represented at a higher rate in terms of marital status. In terms of age distribution, it is understood that the most intense group is in the 31-40 age range, and in terms of education level, bachelor's degree graduates are predominant. In terms of experience, the 6-10 year range represents the highest rate, while in terms of income level, it is seen that a significant portion of the participants are concentrated in the middle income range.

Various statistical measures are used to assess the validity, reliability, and internal consistency of scales. The most commonly used methods in this context are Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. Cronbach's Alpha, ρ_A , and CR values are expected to be above 0.70, and the AVE value is expected to be above 0.50. In addition, the CR value should be greater than the AVE value in order to ensure convergent validity. Details of the analysis results, validity, and reliability values obtained from the scales and descriptive statistical values are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Factor Loadings, Reliability, Validity, and Descriptive Statistics of the Scales

Items	Factor Loadings	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	VIF
Sustainable Leadership Scale						
Cronbach's Alpha= 0.831, rho_A=0.831 CR=0.877, AVE=0.542						
SL1	0.712	3.187	1.349	-0.176	-1.130	1.529
SL2	0.732	3.236	1.372	-0.198	-1.163	1.672
SL 3	0.742	3.231	1.344	-0.197	-1.125	1.621
SL 4	0.782	3.226	1.336	-0.154	-1.138	1.799
SL 5	0.723	3.078	1.372	-0.027	-1.219	1.599
SL 6	0.725	3.073	1.376	-0.098	-1.219	1.578
Green Creativity Scale						
Cronbach's Alpha= 0.831, rho_A=0.833 CR=0.877, AVE=0.543						
GC1	0.688	3.161	1.424	-0.163	-1.275	1.484
GC2	0.748	2.990	1.345	0.054	-1.191	1.680
GC3	0.793	3.075	1.307	-0.035	-1.117	1.846
GC4	0.742	2.956	1.361	0.039	-1.202	1.627
GC5	0.717	3.080	1.358	-0.046	-1.197	1.574
GC6	0.730	3.092	1.351	-0.097	-1.165	1.545
Green Organizational Identity Scale						
Cronbach's Alpha = 0.802, rho_A=0.807, CR=0.858, AVE=0.503						
GOI1	0.648	3.139	1.357	-0.118	-1.193	1.339
GOI2	0.694	3.117	1.374	-0.081	-1.223	1.475
GOI3	0.733	3.100	1.309	-0.008	-1.117	1.553
GOI4	0.755	3.148	1.303	-0.097	-1.102	1.584
GOI5	0.744	3.182	1.315	-0.133	-1.099	1.558
GOI6	0.676	2.917	1.377	0.048	-1.238	1.414
Corporate Social Responsibility Scale						
Cronbach's Alpha = 0.808, rho_A=0.811, CR=0.867, AVE=0.565						
CSR1	0.755	3.027	1.331	0.007	-1.139	1.581
CSR2	0.794	3.078	1.317	-0.137	-1.074	1.675
CSR3	0.743	3.131	1.364	-0.140	-1.179	1.528
CSR4	0.732	3.229	1.331	-0.293	-1.020	1.511
CSR5	0.733	3.090	1.343	-0.019	-1.166	1.533

SL=Sustainable Leadership, GC=Green Creativity, GOI=Green Organizational Identity, CSR=Corporate Social Responsibility

Source: Authors' Calculations.

Table 2 presents the factor loadings, reliability, and validity indicators, and descriptive statistics of the scales used in the study. When the findings are analyzed, it is seen that the factor loadings of the items in all scales are within acceptable limits. The factor loadings for the Sustainable Leadership Scale ranged between 0.712 and 0.782, and the reliability coefficients of the scale were calculated as Cronbach's Alpha=0.831, rho_A=0.831, and CR=0.877. In addition, the AVE value of 0.542 indicates that the convergent validity of the scale was achieved. The mean values of the items ranged between 3.07 and 3.23, and the standard deviation values were between 1.33 and 1.37. The fact that the skewness and kurtosis values are in the range of ± 2 indicates that the data are close to a normal distribution. The fact that the VIF values are in the range of 1.52-1.67 reveals that there is no multicollinearity problem. When the Green Creativity Scale is analyzed, it is seen that the factor loadings of the items vary between 0.688 and 0.793. The reliability coefficients of the scale were determined as Cronbach's Alpha=0.831, rho_A=0.833, and CR=0.877, and the AVE value was calculated as 0.543. These findings show that the scale is a reliable and valid measurement tool. The mean values of the items of the scale ranged between 2.95 and 3.16, while the standard deviation values were in the range of 1.30-1.42. The fact that the skewness and kurtosis values are within acceptable limits shows that the distribution of the data is at an acceptable normal level. Likewise, VIF values in the range of 1.48-1.84 indicate that there is no multicollinearity problem among the variables.

The factor loadings for the Green Organizational Identity Scale ranged between 0.648 and 0.755. The reliability coefficients of the scale were calculated as Cronbach's Alpha=0.802, rho_A=0.807, and CR=0.858, and the AVE value of 0.503 indicates that convergent validity was achieved. The mean values for the items ranged between 2.91 and 3.18, while the standard deviation values were in the range of 1.30-1.37. When the skewness and kurtosis values are analyzed, it is seen that all items are within the normal distribution limits. In addition, VIF values in the range of 1.33-1.58 indicate that there is no multicollinearity problem among the variables. Finally, when the Corporate Social Responsibility Scale is analyzed, it is seen that the factor loadings of the items vary between 0.732 and 0.794. The reliability coefficients of the scale were calculated as Cronbach's Alpha=0.808, rho_A=0.811, and CR=0.867, and the AVE value of 0.565 indicates that convergent validity was achieved. The mean values of the items are between 3.03 and 3.23, and the standard deviation values vary between 1.33 and 1.36. Skewness and kurtosis values are within acceptable limits and show that the data are close to a normal distribution. In addition, VIF values are in the range of 1.52-1.67, indicating that there is no multicollinearity problem. In general, it is understood that the scales used in the study meet the reliability and validity criteria, and the data set is suitable for statistical analysis. In order to evaluate the discriminant validity, Fornell-Larcker Criterion and HTMT values were examined, and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Fornell-Larcker Criterion and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) Values

	Fornell-Larcker Criterion				Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
CSR	0.752				1.000			
SL	0.654	0.736			0.362	1.000		
GOI	0.575	0.703	0.709		0.307	0.367	1.000	
GC	0.559	0.662	0.659	0.737	0.309	0.359	0.345	1.000

Source: Authors' Calculations.

Table 3 presents the Fornell-Larcker criterion and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) values for the variables in the research model. According to the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the root AVE value of each construct should be higher than the correlation values between other constructs. When the table is analyzed, it is seen that the values of CSR (0.752), SL (0.736), GOI (0.709), and GC (0.737) are higher than the other correlation values in the relevant rows and columns. This situation shows that the discriminant validity between the variables is ensured. In addition, it was determined that the HTMT values ranged between 0.307 and 0.367, and all values were well below the accepted threshold value (0.90). These findings reveal that discriminant validity is achieved between the variables in the research model. Table 4 below shows the goodness-of-fit values obtained from the research model.

Table 4. Goodness-of-Fit Values

Items	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR<0.080	0.056	0.059
d_ ULS	0.854	0.965
d_ G	0.240	0.246
Chi-Square<5	562.856	570.355
NFI>0.80	0.855	0.853

Source: Authors' Calculations.

Table 4 presents the goodness-of-fit values for the research model. When the findings are examined, it is seen that the SRMR value is below the accepted threshold value (<0.080) for both the saturated model (0.056) and the estimated model (0.059). The d_ ULS and d_ G values were calculated as 0.854 and 0.240 for the saturated model and 0.965 and 0.246 for the estimated model, respectively. In addition, the NFI value used to evaluate the model fit was above 0.80 in both models (0.855 and 0.853). Chi-Square values were 562.856 and 570.355, respectively. In general, the obtained goodness-of-fit indicators show that the research model provides an acceptable level of fit with the data. Table 5 below shows the structural equation model coefficients.

Figure 2. Path Diagram

Source: Authors' Calculations.

According to the research model in Figure 2, sustainable leadership positively affects both green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility. In addition, it is determined that sustainable leadership has a direct positive effect on green creativity. In the model, green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility play a mediating role in the relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity. When the structural model is examined, it is seen that the effect of sustainable leadership on green organizational identity is $\beta=0.706$, its effect on corporate social responsibility is $\beta=0.655$, and its direct effect on green creativity is $\beta=0.314$. In addition, the effect of green organizational identity on green creativity is $\beta=0.357$, and the effect of corporate social responsibility is $\beta=0.149$. When the explanatory levels in the model are examined, it is seen that green organizational identity is explained by $R^2=0.498$, corporate social responsibility by $R^2=0.429$, and green creativity by $R^2=0.530$. These results show that the structural relationships in the model are significant and the level of explanatory power is moderate. The findings regarding the research hypotheses are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Hypothesis Test Results

Paths	β	Standard Deviation	t-value	95% Bca CI	P-value	Hypotheses
SL→GOI	0.706	0.032	21.817	(0.646; 0.759)	0.000	H1 Accept
SL→CSR	0.655	0.037	17.662	(0.582;0.724)	0.000	H2 Accept
SL→GC	0.314	0.055	5.724	(0.206;0.418)	0.000	H3 Accept

GOI→GC	0.357	0.053	6.746	(0.256;0.455)	0.000	H4 Accept
CSR→GC	0.149	0.050	2.956	(0.053;0.250)	0.003	H5 Accept
SL→GOI→GC	0.252	0.048	5.250	(0.161;0.344)	0.000	H6 Accept (Partial)
SL→CSR→GC	0.098	0.034	2.882	(0.032;0.166)	0.000	H7 Accept (Partial)

Source: Authors' Calculations.

Table 5 presents the results of the structural equation model (SEM) analysis of the hypotheses in the research model. When the findings are examined, the effect of sustainable leadership on green organizational identity was found to be positive and significant ($\beta=0.706$, $t=21.817$, $p<0.001$). This result supports hypothesis H1 and shows that an increase in the level of sustainable leadership increases employees' perception of green organizational identity. Similarly, the effect of sustainable leadership on corporate social responsibility is positive and significant ($\beta=0.655$, $t=17.662$, $p<0.001$). This finding supports hypothesis H2 and reveals that sustainable leadership practices strengthen the perception of social responsibility in organizations.

In the research model, the direct effect of sustainable leadership on green creativity was also significant ($\beta=0.314$, $t=5.724$, $p<0.001$). This result supports hypothesis H3 and shows that sustainable leadership practices can increase employees' environmentally oriented creative behaviors. Moreover, the effect of green organizational identity on green creativity is positive and significant ($\beta=0.357$, $t=6.746$, $p<0.001$). This finding supports hypothesis H4 and shows that employees' identification of their organizations with an environmentally friendly identity increases their green creativity behaviors.

In addition, the effect of corporate social responsibility on green creativity is also significant ($\beta=0.149$, $t=2.956$, $p=0.003$). This result supports hypothesis H5 and shows that social responsibility activities of organizations play a positive role in employees' developing innovative thoughts towards the environment.

When the mediation relationships in the model are examined, it is determined that the indirect effect of sustainable leadership on green creativity through green organizational identity is significant ($\beta=0.252$, $t=5.250$, $p<0.001$). This finding supports hypothesis H6 and shows that green organizational identity plays a partial mediating role in the effect of sustainable leadership on green creativity. Similarly, the indirect effect of sustainable leadership on green creativity through corporate social responsibility was also significant ($\beta=0.098$, $t=2.882$, $p<0.001$). This result supports hypothesis H7 and reveals that corporate social responsibility also plays a partial mediating role in the effect of sustainable leadership on green creativity. In structural equation modeling, the R^2 value is calculated to determine the explanatory level of the model. R^2 value, which varies between 0 and 1, shows the power of the model to explain the variance in the

dependent variable. The findings regarding the R^2 values calculated in this context are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. R2 and Q2 Values

Items	R^2	R^2 Adj.	Q^2
GC	0.530	0.527	0.283
GOI	0.498	0.497	0.247
CSR	0.429	0.428	0.240

Source: Authors' Calculations.

The explanatory power of the structural equation model was evaluated with the R^2 and adjusted R^2 (R^2 Adj.) values calculated for the dependent variables. These values show the extent to which the independent variables in the model explain the total variance in the relevant dependent variable. Within the scope of the model, the R^2 value of the green creativity variable was calculated as 0.530, and the adjusted R^2 value was calculated as 0.527. This finding shows that sustainable leadership, green organizational identity, and corporate social responsibility variables in the model explain approximately 53% of the total variance in green creativity. This reveals that the model has a medium-high level of explanatory power on green creativity.

The R^2 value for the green organizational identity variable was calculated as 0.498, and the adjusted R^2 value as 0.497. This result shows that the sustainable leadership variable explains approximately 50% of the variance in green organizational identity. This value shows that the model has a moderate explanatory power on the green organizational identity variable.

The R^2 value for the corporate social responsibility variable was found to be 0.429, and the adjusted R^2 value was 0.428. This finding shows that the sustainable leadership variable explains approximately 43% of the variance in corporate social responsibility. This result reveals that the model has a moderate explanatory power in terms of the corporate social responsibility variable. In general, the R^2 and adjusted R^2 values obtained show that the research model can explain the relevant variables at medium and medium-high levels and that the model has a sufficient explanatory power. In addition, the Q^2 values in the table ($GC=0.283$, $GOI=0.247$, $CSR=0.240$) are greater than zero, indicating that the model has sufficient predictive power for the relevant variables.

6. Conclusion and Discussion

In this study, the impact of sustainable leadership on green creativity was examined, and the mediating roles of green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility in this relationship were analyzed. Research findings show that sustainable leadership affects employees' green creativity level both directly and indirectly. In addition, it was determined that sustainable leadership strengthens

employees' perceptions of environmental identity towards their organizations and their understanding of corporate social responsibility. The results reveal that a sustainable leadership approach plays an important role in the development of environmental awareness and innovative behaviors in organizations.

According to the results of the study, the effect of sustainable leadership on green organizational identity was found to be strong and significant. This finding shows that sustainable leadership practices contribute to employees' perception of their organization as an environmentally sensitive organization. This finding is in line with the studies in the literature that show that sustainable leadership strengthens employees' environmental values and organizational identity perceptions. Sustainable leaders contribute to shaping the psychological bond that employees establish with the organization within the framework of environmental values by promoting environmental responsibility awareness within the organization. This situation enables employees to perceive their organization as an environmentally sensitive institution and adopt this identity.

Another important finding of the study is the positive and significant effect of sustainable leadership on corporate social responsibility. This result shows that sustainable leadership plays an important role in the development of social and environmental responsibility activities in organizations. In the literature, it is stated that sustainable leaders adopt a management approach that cares not only about economic performance but also about environmental and social responsibilities. In this context, sustainable leaders lead organizations to develop environmentally sensitive policies and increase social responsibility activities. Research findings are consistent with this approach and reveal that sustainable leadership strengthens the perception of corporate social responsibility.

The research findings also show that sustainable leadership has a direct impact on green creativity. This result suggests that sustainable leadership practices encourage employees to develop innovative ideas focused on the environment. Green creativity refers to employees' developing new and innovative solutions to environmental problems. Sustainable leaders encourage employees to be sensitive to environmental problems and contribute to the development of environmentally focused, innovative thinking within the organization. Studies in the literature that leadership approaches increase the creativity level of employees support this finding. In this context, it can be said that sustainable leadership is an important factor that encourages employees' environmentally innovative behaviors.

Another important finding of the study is the significant effect of green organizational identity on green creativity. This result shows that employees' perception of their organization as an environmentally sensitive organization can increase environmentally innovative behaviors. Organizational identity is an important indicator of the psychological bond that employees establish with their organizations. Employees' perception of their organization as an environmentally responsible organization may contribute to their motivation to develop innovative

ideas for the environment. This situation paves the way for the development of environment-oriented creativity within the organization.

Similarly, corporate social responsibility has a significant effect on green creativity. Corporate social responsibility activities contribute to employees' perception that their organizations fulfill their responsibilities towards the environment and society. This situation may help employees to develop positive attitudes towards their organizations and exhibit environment-oriented innovative behaviors. In this context, the research findings reveal that corporate social responsibility practices are an important factor that supports green creativity in organizations. The study also revealed that green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility play a mediating role in the relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity. This finding suggests that sustainable leadership affects employees' green creativity behaviors not only directly but also through organizational processes. In other words, sustainable leadership practices indirectly contribute to the development of green creativity by strengthening employees' perceptions of environmental identity and social responsibility towards their organizations. This result makes an important contribution to the literature explaining the effects of sustainable leadership on organizational behavior.

From a theoretical perspective, the study makes important contributions to the sustainable leadership literature. First, the study reveals how sustainable leadership affects not only environmental performance or organizational outcomes but also employees' environmentally oriented creative behaviors. Secondly, the study contributes to filling the conceptual gap in the literature by explaining the role of green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility in the relationship between sustainable leadership and green creativity. In this respect, the study contributes to the development of sustainable leadership and environmental organizational behavior literature.

Research findings also have important implications for practitioners. Adopting a sustainable leadership approach, especially for businesses operating in the aviation sector, can contribute to the development of environmentally focused innovative behaviors. Managers' adoption of a sustainability-oriented leadership approach may encourage employees to develop creative solutions to environmental problems. In addition, making environmental values a part of corporate identity in organizations can strengthen employees' bond with the organization and support green creativity. In addition, increasing the environmental and social responsibility activities of organizations may contribute to employees' positive perception of their organizations and exhibit environmentally oriented innovative behaviors.

As a result, this study reveals that sustainable leadership plays an important role in increasing employees' green creativity behaviors. In addition, green organizational identity and corporate social responsibility were found to be important mediating mechanisms in this relationship. These findings suggest that sustainable leadership practices can contribute to the development of environment-

oriented innovative behaviors by increasing environmental awareness in organizations. In this respect, the study makes important contributions to the literature on sustainable leadership and environmental organizational behavior.

Research results also reveal important implications for practitioners. Especially in the aviation sector, the adoption of a sustainable leadership approach can encourage employees' environmentally oriented innovative behaviors. Managers exhibiting leadership behaviors that support environmental sustainability and increase the social responsibility activities of organizations can contribute to the development of environment-oriented creativity in organizations. In this direction, developing organizational policies that support sustainable leadership practices can contribute to achieving environmental sustainability goals.

This study has some limitations. First of all, the study was conducted with data obtained from employees operating in a specific sector. This may limit the generalization of the findings to different sectors. In addition, the data was collected through a survey method and is based on the subjective evaluations of the participants, which may reveal the risk of common method bias. In addition, the research model is limited to the variables of sustainable leadership, green organizational identity, corporate social responsibility, and green creativity. In future research, testing the model in different sectors and including different variables such as organizational support, environmental awareness, or green innovation in the model may contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the relationships between sustainable leadership and environmental organizational behaviors.

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